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“SEVEN SILLY DOGS”

I have four dogs I love so much,
With wagging tails and playful touch.
Dodong barks at passing bikes,
While Carla chews on all the likes!

Popol runs like he's in a race,
But always ends up in the wrong place.
Inday sleeps the whole day long,
Unless she hears a food bowl song!

Then there are three—oh, who are they?
They showed up here one rainy day.
No names yet, but they don't mind,
They eat, they nap, they're sweet and kind.

One has ears as big as plates,
One just spins and chases gates.
The third one loves to steal my sock—
Then hides behind a flower pot rock!

Seven tails, a happy crew,
They bark, they jump, they pee on shoes.
But still I love them, every one,
My silly pack, my joy, my fun!